

Guide for researchers to implement **FAIR Workflows**

Conventional research practice tends to focus on research articles and withhold the procedural documents, supporting datasets, and other relevant materials generated during the research process. However, the limitations of this approach have become increasingly apparent due to phenomena such as 'publish or perish,' the reproducibility crisis, and instances of academic fraud. In response, the research community is advocating for greater accountability, transparency, and openness. This call is being met by various initiatives across disciplinary domains, all aimed at making research data and supporting resources FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. In this guide, we outline steps researchers can take to share all their research outputs with PIDs and metadata to make their research process and practices FAIR.

Benefits of incorporating FAIR Workflows

Collaboration: Science thrives on collaboration. Even when working independently, your research can benefit others. Sharing work, processes, results, and providing context to make them FAIR are the initial steps toward fostering successful collaboration.

Crediting: Every stage of research merits recognition. By showcasing the extensive work throughout the research process, including creating tangible outputs and attributing them to the individuals and organizations involved, we can effectively acknowledge contributions and demonstrate impact.

Compliance: Adhering to best practices is essential. Planning and executing each stage of research with the FAIR principles in mind helps navigate policies and requirements from institutes, funders, and collaborators. This proactive approach streamlines data sharing, reporting, and preservation efforts.

Central to achieving FAIR and Open research are persistent identifiers (PIDs). These identifiers and their associated metadata play a crucial role in each aspect of FAIR, through facilitating the discoverability, provenance tracking, and preservation of research outputs. By utilizing PIDs and standardized metadata in the sharing process, researchers can effectively describe and connect their outputs, thereby enhancing their FAIRness.

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A primer of the FAIR principles for researchers

Making scholarly works Findable involves making them available as scholarly records, ensuring they can be indexed and searched. The most comprehensive index for scholarly works is generated from DOI metadata.

Making scholarly works Accessible entails providing a pathway to make the work available to others. This can be achieved by depositing the work in a scholarly repository or utilizing platforms that host works and facilitate DOI registration for completed works.

Making scholarly works Interoperable means to describe them with standardized metadata and create meaningful links among related works so that they can be incorporated into different settings - this can be done by indicating relationships to other works during the sharing/deposition process.

Making scholarly works Reusable indicates to provide sufficient context for each individual work so that it can be understood and responsibly applied in subsequent research - this requires outputs be annotated with licensing, provenance, and community standards information in the PID metadata.

In order to align with the FAIR principles, it's crucial for researchers to make certain research objects, typically hidden away, available as reusable outputs.

The DOI and metadata created in the submission and sharing process is what makes an output FAIR. DOI metadata describes the work itself, and enables connections to related people, organizations, and funding through their corresponding PIDs. The PID infrastructure supports interoperability and facilitates discoverability of scholarly resources on a global scale - and makes diverse types of scholarly works easily citable.

FAIR sharing through the stages of the research project

	WHY The goals of sharing outputs in this stage	WHAT Sharable outputs and examples of supporting tools and platforms	HOW Workflows to ensure FAIRness of shared outputs
PROJECT PLANNING	Create points of reference through which all relevant outputs of the project can be linked and discovered	PROJECT PAGE E.g. Open Science Framework	Use tools/platforms that are integrated with open infrastructure to create and share outputs Register DOIs for each output
	Provide a shared understanding for expected FAIR practices in the project	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN E.g. DMP Tool ARGOS	Use PIDs to reference related people, organizations, and resources in the metadata
METHOD PLANNING	Increase credibility and create guardrail against bad practice	PREREGISTRATION E.g. Open Science Framework	All of the above, and Reference the project and/or DMP in the DOI metadata when registering new outputs
	Enhance reproducibility and reusability through the implementation of domain specific metadata standard	METADATA TEMPLATE E.g. CEDAR Workbench	
EXPERIMENT & ANALYSIS	Follow up on the registered activities and mark deviations	EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL E.g. protocols.io	All of the above, and Reference corresponding registration in the DOI metadata when registering new outputs Create references among related data/code/protocol in the metadata
	Create robust records to supplement research outcome	ANALYSIS CODE AND SOFTWARE E.g. Zenodo	
	Credit all contributors in the research process	DATASET E.g. Dryad	
DISSEMINATION	Expedite dissemination of project outputs	PREPRINT E.g. PsyArXiv bioRxiv	All of the above, and Cite shared outputs by their DOIs in manuscripts and presentations
	Invite community engagement and feedback	PRESENTATION E.g. Zenodo Figshare	
	Lower barriers to access	PAPER E.g. ChronosHub	

